

1 **Livestock disease resilience: from individual to herd level**

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13 **Abstract**

14 Infectious diseases are a major threat to the sustainable production of high-producing
15 animals. Control efforts, such as veterinary vaccines or breeding approaches often
16 target improvement of animals' resilience to infections, i.e. they strengthen the animals'
17 ability to cope with infections, rather than protecting them from infection *per se*. Alerted
18 by the devastating effects of individuals that are highly resilient to the infectious agent
19 of COVID-19 (i.e. asymptomatic carriers that become infected and infectious, but don't
20 develop disease signs) on global human health and economy, we strongly advocate a
21 shift of focus from increasing the disease resilience of individual animals to herd
22 disease resilience as the appropriate target for sustainable disease control in livestock.
23 Herd resilience not captures the direct effects of vaccination or host genetics on
24 animals' own health and production performance, but also the indirect effects on the
25 environmental pathogen load that herd members are exposed to. The latter is

26 mediated by individuals' susceptibility to infection and by their infectiousness when
27 infected. We review what is currently known about how vaccination or selective
28 breeding as two important disease control methods affect herd resilience and its
29 underlying components, and outline the changes required to current vaccination and
30 breeding approaches in order to effectively improve herd resilience. To this purpose
31 we also seek to clarify and harmonise the terminology used in the different animal
32 science disciplines to facilitate future collaborative combined approaches to infectious
33 disease control in livestock.

34

35 **Keywords:** Resilience, infectious disease, pathogen transmission, disease
36 resistance, tolerance, vaccine efficacy, breeding, livestock, production animals

37 **Implications**

38 Vaccination and breeding programmes that target improvement of herd resilience will
39 lead to more effective control of infectious diseases in production animals, as they
40 not only reduce the impact of infectious pathogens on individuals' health and
41 production performance but also their spread.

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Infectious diseases are one of the biggest threats to sustainable livestock production,
44 especially for high-performance animals which are commonly reared in confined
45 environments that foster pathogen transmission (Lindström et al. 2012; Craft 2015).
46 Climate change, antimicrobial resistance and recent modifications in agricultural
47 practices and demography have been shown to exacerbate pathogen burden (Tomley
48 and Shirley 2009). Hence, more than ever, effective disease control is paramount for

49 a healthy agronomy, for national and international food security and for alleviating
50 poverty in developing countries (Tomley and Shirley 2009).

51 Next to biosecurity, vaccination and selective breeding for increased disease
52 resistance constitute the main preventive measures against infectious diseases in
53 farmed livestock. However, neither currently available veterinary vaccines nor the
54 animals' natural genetic makeup usually confer full resistance to infection (Meeusen et
55 al. 2007). Many veterinary vaccines, as well as breeding programmes, mitigate the
56 impact of infection on health and production performance of animals by improving their
57 ability to cope with infection rather than protecting animals from infection as such
58 (Meeusen et al. 2007; Vale et al. 2016). In other words, they aim to increase the
59 disease resilience of animals, which has been broadly defined as the ability of animals
60 to cope with infectious challenge (Bisset and Morrison 1996) or more explicitly for
61 production animals as the ability of animals to maintain high production performance
62 when challenged by infection (Albers et al. 1987). In a rapidly changing and
63 increasingly connected world that fosters the circulation of existing and newly emerging
64 pathogens across regions, countries and continents, a strong capacity to cope with
65 infections seems indeed vital.

66
67 The current global COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, provides
68 an interesting example of the differing perspectives of disease resilience and
69 resistance to infection that is very relevant to livestock systems for high-producing
70 animals. For this pathogen, approximately 40% to 45% of infected individuals have
71 been estimated to be asymptomatic, that is, infectious for some period of time but
72 without any symptoms suggestive of disease (Oran and Topol 2020). In other words,
73 these individuals are both susceptible to infection and disease resilient. Whilst clearly

74 beneficial for their own health and well-being, these disease resilient individuals are
75 infectious and impose a substantial threat to the health of others who they come into
76 contact with. The presence of asymptomatic individuals has raised major challenges
77 for effective COVID-19 control, which causes unprecedented disruptions to all sectors
78 of life in severely affected countries and devastating long-term effects on global health
79 and the global economy (Nikolai et al 2020, Rahimi and Abadi, 2020).

80 For farmed animals, the role of these disease-resilient individuals in COVID-19 spread
81 provokes a potential re-thinking of our current approaches to improve livestock disease
82 resilience. Important questions to be posed include: “How do disease-resilient
83 individuals affect the environmental pathogen landscape?” and “Is there a risk that
84 improvements in disease resilience, as opposed to resistance to infection, might
85 inadvertently increase pathogen spread and hence jeopardizes disease resilience at
86 the population level, i.e. the ‘herd resilience’?”. It is timely to consider the potential
87 impact of current approaches to improve disease resilience of individual animals, both
88 with respect to the environmental pathogen load and to population-level disease
89 severity.

90
91 In this paper, we approach the above questions by advocating a more explicit shift from
92 increasing the disease resilience of individual animals to herd disease resilience as the
93 appropriate target for sustainable disease control of livestock. We demonstrate that
94 herd disease resilience is not just the average resilience of its herd members, but also
95 contains additional components relevant to pathogen load, including individual
96 susceptibility to infection and the magnitude and duration of infectiousness among
97 those individuals that do become infected. We introduce the underlying animal intrinsic
98 component traits of herd disease resilience and review what is known about how

99 vaccination or selective breeding affect herd resilience and its underlying components.

100 Based on the outcomes, we propose future avenues towards more effective
101 vaccination and breeding programmes for improving herd resilience.

102 This review also aims to unite concepts and research findings from diverse research
103 disciplines (e.g. animal production science, infection and immunity, epidemiology,
104 vaccinology, animal breeding), which often differ in the terminology used. We therefore
105 provide a glossary of terms used in this perspectives paper (Table 1).

106

107 **INSERT TABLE 1 HERE**

108

109 **2. Herd resilience instead of individual resilience as a target for effective**

110 **disease control**

111

112 Resilience can be an attribute of an individual animal (*individual resilience*), a herd
113 (*herd resilience*) or an entire production system (*system resilience*) (Table 1). In the
114 context of livestock production, disease resilience has been broadly defined as the
115 ability of an animal, a herd (a group of animals) or an entire production system (several
116 herds) to maintain high production performance while challenged by infection (after
117 Bisset and Morris, 1996). More specifically, resilience is the capacity to be minimally
118 affected by exposure to infection or to rapidly return to the pre-exposure state (after
119 Colditz and Hine, 2016).

120 Quantitatively, the disease resilience of a production animal can be measured in terms
121 of the reduction in health, fitness or production performance (reduced from the level
122 expressed in the absence of infection) when exposed to infection (Bisset & Morris,
123 1996). In other words, more resilient individuals deviate less from their health, fitness

124 or performance potential. The magnitude of reduction depends on factors relating to
125 the host (e.g. the individual's resistance and tolerance, as defined in Table 1), and on
126 the pathogen load that it is exposed to (Knap and Doeschl-Wilson, 2020). Therefore,
127 individuals' disease resilience is conventionally modelled as the reaction norm of the
128 individual's health or performance on environmental pathogen load (Knap and
129 Doeschl-Wilson, 2020).

130 Individuals are known to vary genetically in their response to pathogens, and thus in
131 their disease resilience. Incomplete vaccine coverage or heterogeneous vaccine
132 response may further exacerbate this variation between individual herd members.

133 It is important to note that herd resilience does not equal the average individual
134 resilience of the animals in the herd. Blanc et al. (2013) made an explicit distinction
135 between herd resilience and individual resilience: "herd resilience depends on the
136 adaptive capacity of the animals in the herd [i.e. on individual resilience], together with
137 the management decisions that affect the performance trajectories and local
138 environment of the animals". In the context of infectious disease, the crucial component
139 of this "local environment of the animals" is the pathogen load that they are exposed
140 to (hereafter denoted as *environmental pathogen load*). Each infected animal can
141 contribute to the environmental pathogen load, with the potential to indirectly affect the
142 health and performance of susceptible, in-contact animals. Hence, herd resilience as
143 a whole is more than the sum of its components (the resilience of all individuals in the
144 herd) as it also contains a component that determines the transmission of infectious
145 pathogens among animals within the herd.

146

147 **INSERT FIGURE 1 HERE**

148

149 Figure 1 illustrates how individual resilience factors interact with those epidemiological
150 factors relating to environmental pathogen load, to determine herd resilience. As a
151 broad principle, animals in a herd exposed to infectious pathogens may transition
152 between three infection states: Susceptible (S), Infected and Infectious (I), and
153 Recovered (R). The health, fitness or production performance of infected and
154 recovered animals may be reduced relative to their performance in the absence of
155 infection, and this depends partly on their multi-faceted individual resilience as
156 mentioned above. The epidemiological component of herd resilience describes how
157 individuals contribute to the environmental pathogen load, with potential implications
158 for susceptible herd members. In the context of the SIR model (Fig. 1), each
159 individual's relative contribution to herd resilience depends on (i) its *susceptibility* to
160 infection (which also directly affects individual resilience), as well as (ii) its *infectivity*
161 (i.e. magnitude of infectiousness, Table 1), and (iii) the duration of its *infectious period*
162 (i.e. the inverse of its *recovery rate* in SIR models, i.e. if the duration of the infectious
163 period and the duration of disease are equal).

164 Animals are known to vary not only in their individual disease resilience but also in
165 those epidemiological traits relating to environmental pathogen load (VanderWaal and
166 Exanwa, 2016; Anacleto et al., [2018](#)[2019](#)). Effective disease control that targets herd
167 resilience could thus target improvement in individuals' resilience or any combination
168 of the three above-mentioned epidemiological animal traits, crucially without negatively
169 impacting the others. For example, it is not particularly useful to produce highly
170 resilient animals that can cope with a high pathogen load if such animals also act as
171 highly infectious super-spreaders that shed and transmit large amounts of pathogens
172 (Gopinath et al., 2014, Beldomenico, 2020). In contrast, approaches that reduce the
173 environmental pathogen load (general biosecurity measures, vaccination, and animal

174 breeding to reduce individual susceptibility to infection, infectivity and/or duration of the
175 infectious period) will increase herd disease resilience, even when the average disease
176 resilience of individuals is low.

177

178

179 ***Quantifying herd resilience traits***

180 The above-mentioned herd resilience component traits are difficult to measure directly
181 and thus may need to be estimated from available data. Knap and Doeschl-Wilson
182 (2020) provide a review of current methods for estimating individual disease resilience.
183 Estimates for the epidemiological traits related to pathogen transmission could be
184 obtained by assessing pathogen shedding from infectious individuals (e.g. quantity and
185 duration of detectable levels of pathogen in blood, tissues or feces or saliva (Pileri &
186 Mateu, 2016; Tsairidou et al., 2019)). However, such measures are not always
187 available. Also, they may not necessarily correspond to actual transmission patterns,
188 which also depend on individuals' contact behaviour and environmental characteristics
189 (Anderson & May, 1991). Instead, appropriate experimental or field study designs,
190 coupled with statistical inference methods should be used to estimate individual's
191 susceptibility and infectiousness directly from individuals' infection or survival status
192 (Longini et al. 1998; Aznar et al. 2011; Pooley et al. 2020).

193 The impact of interventions on the spread of infection are often quantified at a
194 population level. The measure used for this purpose is the reproduction ratio R , which
195 is defined as the average number of secondary cases produced by a typical infectious
196 individual during its infectious lifetime (Diekman et al. 1990). All disease control
197 strategies aim to reduce R to a threshold value below 1, when the infection can no
198 longer sustainably spread. It is commonly known that individuals can strongly differ in

199 their contribution to R , through variation in susceptibility and magnitude and duration
200 of infectiousness (Lloyd-Smith et al. 2005; VanderWaal and Exanwa, 2016; Anacleto
201 et al 2019). Estimation of R , and of individuals' contribution to it, requires expertise in
202 epidemiological modelling and statistical inference techniques.

203

204 **3. Effects of vaccines on herd resilience**

205 Vaccination is one of the key tools available to control infectious diseases in livestock.
206 Based on recent estimates, vaccines are available for over 400 diseases affecting
207 mammals, birds and fish (Knight-Jones et al., 2014). Within the livestock production
208 sector, some of the most widely used vaccine applications include those against foot-
209 and-mouth disease (FMD) in cattle, sheep, goats and pigs, the Porcine Reproductive
210 Syndrome in pigs and Marek's disease in poultry (Knight-Jones and Rushton 2013;
211 Tizard 2021; Witter 2001). In general, veterinary vaccines improve animal disease
212 resilience by either reducing or eliminating the adverse effects that infection causes on
213 their health and survival, or their productive performance (Knight-Jones et al., 2014).
214 Whilst most vaccines reduce the probability of disease when infected (Table 1),
215 surprisingly few livestock vaccines have been shown to protect animals from becoming
216 infected or from transmitting the pathogens to other animals.

217 ***Vaccine efficacy and effectiveness in the context of herd resilience***

218 The degree to which a vaccine boosts the disease resilience of individuals, the so-
219 called *direct effect of vaccination*, is routinely assessed in vaccine efficacy studies,
220 which are compulsory for licensing a vaccine. The efficacy of a veterinary vaccine is
221 evaluated as "the ability of the vaccine to give protection against adverse effects of the

222 infection to the vaccinated animal” (Pastoret 1997). It is typically assessed through
223 challenge studies in which cohorts of vaccinated and non-vaccinated individuals are
224 infected (usually through individual inoculation) with the target pathogen under
225 controlled experimental conditions, and the health and performance status of these
226 two cohorts is subsequently compared.

227 Vaccine effectiveness refers to the performance of the vaccine under real-world
228 conditions (Shim and Galvani 2014), and accounts for both vaccine efficacy and
229 vaccination coverage (the percentage of the population vaccinated) (Table 1). In real-
230 world conditions, there is the potential to protect unvaccinated individuals given the
231 presence of vaccinated individuals in a population, the so-called *indirect effect of*
232 *vaccination* (Shim and Galvani 2014). In contrast to direct effects, indirect vaccine
233 effects are mediated by intervention-induced changes in pathogen transmission
234 (Halloran et al., 2010, Bailey et al. [2019/2020](#)). More explicitly, a vaccine is considered
235 as effective, if it can reduce within-host pathogen burden (e.g. through increasing host
236 resistance) as well as pathogen shedding (e.g. through reducing host infectivity or the
237 duration of the infectious period), prevent or alleviate disease-induced clinical signs
238 (e.g. through improving host tolerance), thus improving the general health conditions
239 of the exposed animals (Meeusen et al. 2007). Vaccine effectiveness thus targets herd
240 resilience as it considers the direct vaccine effects on individuals’ own resilience as
241 well as the indirect effect of vaccinated individuals on the performance of others
242 through their contribution to the environmental pathogen load that others are exposed
243 to (Fig. 1).

244 To date, there has been limited consideration of the indirect effects of vaccination for
245 animal health and production. Indeed, there is only a limited literature that explicitly

246 considers the effect of vaccines on pathogen transmission. This is in large part
247 because an assessment of indirect vaccine effects is not required for vaccine
248 authorisation, and because different methodologies are required to measure estimate
249 these effects (Longini et al. 1998; Orsel et al 2007).

250 ***Insights from case studies***

251 There is some published information about the epidemiological effects of vaccines in
252 animal populations, which provides valuable insights into how vaccines may affect herd
253 resilience. Some of these insights for different species are considered below.

254

255 *Bovine tuberculosis in badgers and cattle*

256 Bovine tuberculosis (bTB, caused by infection with *Mycobacterium bovis*) is a zoonotic
257 disease of bovidae (Bezons et al., 2014). Badger to cattle transmission is one of the
258 reasons contributing to difficulties faced in seeking to eradicate bTB from Britain and
259 Ireland (Allen et al. 2018). The only licensed vaccine currently available shown to
260 confer protection against *M. bovis* is the live attenuated Bacille Calmette Guerin (BCG)
261 (Hope and Villarrael-Ramos 2008). Application of this vaccine to cattle is however
262 forbidden under international and EU law because it is not possible to distinguish, in a
263 diagnostic sense, between vaccinated and naturally infected cows. Instead, BCG
264 vaccination of badgers is being used to control *M. bovis* infection in badgers (Aznar et
265 al. 2018), with evidence of beneficial downstream effects on bTB prevalence in cattle
266 (Martin et al. 2020). A BCG badger vaccination field trial conducted in Ireland showed
267 that susceptibility to natural exposure with *M. bovis* was reduced in vaccinated
268 compared to placebo treated badgers with a vaccine efficacy for susceptibility of 59%
269 (Aznar et al. 2018). However, the trial revealed a complete lack of vaccine effect on

270 the infectivity of vaccinated infected badgers, implying that vaccinated badgers were
271 equally infectious as non-vaccinated badgers when naturally infected with *M. bovis*.
272 This lack of indirect vaccination effects on *M. bovis* transmission raises demands on
273 vaccination coverage in badger populations to achieve the desired vaccine
274 effectiveness for eradicating bTB in badgers and cattle (Aznar et al. 2018).

275

276 *FMD in ruminants and monogastrics and PRRS in monogastrics*

277 Foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) affecting cloven-hooved animals, including cattle,
278 sheep, goats and pigs, and the Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome
279 (PRRS) in pigs, constitute two economically important livestock diseases for which the
280 pathological and epidemiological effects of vaccines have been assessed in several
281 experimental and field studies. Both diseases are endemic in many countries
282 worldwide, and although mortality is relatively low, morbidity and infection-induced
283 production losses are high (Knight-Jones and Rushton 2013; Nathues et al. 2017).
284 Disease control in many areas where FMD or PRRS is endemic is generally
285 implemented by means of regular mass vaccination, which has achieved noticeable
286 success in reducing disease-associated production losses (Knight-Jones et al. 2014;
287 Linhares et al. 2015). However, vaccination programmes have also shown variable
288 and often limited success in reducing infection prevalence and have raised concerns
289 about the epidemiological consequences of vaccination and urgent demand for more
290 effective vaccines (Parida 2009; Nan et al. 2017).

291 Existing PRRS or FMD vaccines rarely confer sterilizing immunity for heterologous
292 challenge strains, and thus likely only offer little protection from infection for the cocktail
293 of circulating virus strains that pigs are typically exposed to in the field (Parida 2009;
294 Nan et al. 2017). Using a comprehensive modelling framework for assessing vaccine

295 effectiveness applied to PRRS, Bitsouni et al. (2019) demonstrated that even vaccines
296 that offer no or limited protection from infection can substantially reduce pathogen
297 transmission and even achieve a value for the reproductive ratio R below one if vaccine
298 coverage is high and the vaccine sufficiently reduces host infectivity or speeds up
299 recovery. Numerous FMDV and PRRSV vaccine trials have shown that virus excretion
300 usually reduces by several folds when vaccinated animals are challenged with a
301 heterologous virus strain in comparison to unvaccinated control animals, and that virus
302 loads in blood and other tissues reduce faster to undetectable levels in vaccinated
303 animals (Parida 2009, Pileri and Mateu 2015). Transmission experiments generally
304 confirm that these vaccine effects translate into reduced FMD or PRRS virus
305 transmission, and thus increased herd resilience under natural challenge conditions
306 (see e.g. Orsel et al. 2007; Eblé et al. 2008 and van Roermund et al. 2010 for FMD
307 and Pileri et al. 2016; Chase-Topping et al. 2020 for PRRS). However, there is
308 considerable variation between these experiments with regards to the nature and
309 actual amount of reduction in disease transmission, with R-values often still remaining
310 considerably greater than one in vaccinated groups. For example, Chase-Topping et
311 al. (2020) reported an estimated R-value value well above one in vaccinated pigs with
312 the vaccine primarily reducing the duration of virus shedding of infected pigs. In
313 contrast, in a study by Rose et al. (2015) R was reduced to a value below one by the
314 vaccine, simultaneously reducing the duration of shedding as well as the estimated
315 transmission rate. It would be of benefit if future vaccine evaluations were to
316 disentangle the vaccine effects relevant to individual and herd resilience traits, as also
317 indicated in the modelling framework published by Bitsouni et al. (2019). In particular,
318 closer investigation is needed of the role of infected individuals without clinical signs
319 (i.e. equivalent to the asymptomatic COVID-19 carrier individuals) on disease

320 transmission, noting that the prevalence of non- or subclinical individuals may increase
321 as a consequence of vaccination (Horter et al., 2002; Paton et al. 2018).

322

323 *Marek's disease (MD) in poultry*

324 There is increasing awareness that vaccination may not only affect the host but may
325 also alter the pathogen landscape. Evolutionary theory predicts that leaky vaccines,
326 i.e. those that allow the hosts to survive but do not prevent pathogen spread, may drive
327 pathogen evolution towards increased virulence, thus jeopardizing individuals'
328 resilience in the long-term (Gandon et al. 2001). This is particularly pertinent for
329 Marek's disease (MD) in chicken, where step jumps in virulence of field strains of MD
330 virus were repeatedly observed shortly after release of new vaccines (Witter et al.
331 1997). As MD vaccines only prevent disease and death but allow MD virus replication
332 and transmission, Read et al. (2015) have argued that such leaky vaccines alter the
333 balance of selection between pathogen transmission and virulence by allowing more
334 virulent strains to be transmitted at reduced cost. Whilst plausible, direct empirical
335 evidence from transmission studies that vaccines drive pathogen evolution to higher
336 virulence is still lacking. Recent MD transmission experiments revealed that pathogen
337 transmission from vaccinated hosts can cause dose-dependent reduction in pathogen
338 virulence (Bailey et al., 2020). The study showed that non-vaccinated infected contact
339 birds were less likely to develop disease and shed significantly less virus when
340 exposed to vaccinated rather than non-vaccinated infected shedder birds. These
341 results highlight the need to consider also the indirect effects of vaccination on non-
342 vaccinated herd members, highlighting the urgent need for more elaborate vaccine
343 transmission experiments and field studies to fully determine vaccine effects on MD
344 transmission, virus evolution and herd resilience in the long-term.

345

346 *Infectious diseases in aquaculture*

347 Vaccine use is also becoming more widespread to prevent disease in aquaculture
348 (Dadar et al. 2016), and has been a key reason for the success of salmon cultivation
349 (Somerset et al. 2005). In aquaculture, vaccine efficacy is mostly assessed through
350 reduction in mortality rates in vaccinated populations (Dadar et al. 2016). These often
351 involve so-called bath-challenge experiments, where vaccinated or naïve fish are
352 exposed to antigens released in water, which likely mimic natural infection and
353 transmission more closely than would occur with inoculation methods as used during
354 efficacy studies in other species.

355 Very little is known about the impact of vaccines on pathogen transmission in
356 aquaculture, as in-vivo diagnostics of the infection status rarely exist for these species,
357 and transmission experiments are extremely rare. Recent reviews report that fish
358 vaccines often suffer from low efficacy, i.e. they lead to noticeable reduction but not to
359 zero mortality, indicating that many fish vaccines are leaky and don't prevent pathogen
360 transmission (Adams 2019; Børgwald and Dalmo 2019). This was confirmed in a recent
361 transmission trial that assessed vaccination effects on the transmission of Infectious
362 Salmon Anaemia (ISA) virus in Atlantic salmon, which showed that ISA vaccination did
363 not prevent, but reduced transmission and mortality (Chase-Topping et al. 2021). The
364 study also demonstrates that even small-scale transmission experiments can quantify
365 vaccine effects on disease transmission and herd resilience parameters from mortality
366 records alone when coupled with epidemiological models, as predicted by simulation
367 studies (Pooley et al. 2020).

368

369 In summary, recent studies have demonstrated an indirect vaccine effect in some
370 vaccines that were primarily designed to increase individuals' resilience to infectious
371 disease. Some vaccines may add additional benefits, relevant to herd resilience, by
372 reducing the transmission of infectious pathogens both through increased resistance
373 to infection and reduced infectiousness. For most vaccines however, the
374 epidemiological benefits and evolutionary risks are poorly understood. Routine
375 implementation of transmission experiments, coupled with statistical and
376 epidemiological models in vaccine evaluation studies, would be extremely useful to
377 determine optimal vaccines that simultaneously boost individual and herd resilience to
378 infectious diseases. Furthermore, recent developments in pathogen genome
379 sequencing and phylogenetics should provide valuable insights into the effects of
380 vaccination on the pathogen landscape and the corresponding impact on herd
381 resilience in the long-term (Chong et al. 2010; Hadfield et al. 2018).

382

383 **4. Effects of animal breeding on herd resilience**

384

385 There is overwhelming empirical evidence that animals differ genetically in their
386 response to infectious pathogens (Bishop 2010). However, for each of the prevalent
387 infections of production animals, and similar to vaccination, the natural genetic make-
388 up rarely offers full protection to animals from becoming infected. Thus, even animals
389 with high genetic resistance can be susceptible to infection when exposed, can
390 transmit the pathogen, and contribute to the environmental pathogen load. Hence the
391 epidemiological components introduced in Figure 1 also likely play an important role
392 for genetic improvement of herd resilience. However, this has not yet been fully
393 capitalized by the livestock breeding community.

394

395 ***A brief overview of current breeding practices to control infectious diseases***

396 Genetic disease control, through selective breeding of animals that genetically respond
397 more robustly to infection, has long been proposed as a viable alternative or
398 complement to vaccination (Bisset and Morris, 1996; Stear et al. 2001). Whereas
399 vaccine trials aim to minimise heterogeneity between the animals (Velthuis et al. 2003),
400 animal breeding relies on and utilizes genetic variation to improve the host response
401 to infection from one generation to the next. Despite considerable research
402 investment, to date the livestock breeding sector applies little explicit selection for
403 disease resilience (see Knap and Doeschl-Wilson 2020 for a review and future outlook
404 on this). The primary focus has been on improving animals' disease resistance (see
405 Table 1, animal production and breeding concepts), although the exact definition of
406 'disease resistance' differs in the animal breeding literature across host and pathogen
407 species, with different implications for herd resilience, as will be outlined below.

408 Regardless of the exact definition used, breeding for disease resistance has been
409 implemented in most livestock and aquaculture species (Bishop and Woolliams 2014;
410 Houston 2017), albeit only for a small number of diseases relative to those tackled with
411 vaccination. Successful examples include the national sheep breeding programmes
412 for scrapie resistance in several European countries, or marker-assisted selection for
413 infectious pancreatic necrosis (IPN) resistance in Atlantic salmon and for *E. coli*
414 resistance in pigs. These programmes each resulted in a reduced disease prevalence
415 to acceptably low levels within less than 10 years of selective breeding (Boelaert et al.
416 2016; Hjeltnes 2019; Luther 2018). However, progress with each of these diseases
417 can be attributed to the fortuitous but rare discovery of a single gene with a large effect
418 on disease resistance. For the more common situation of polygenically controlled

419 disease resistance (where resistance is primarily controlled by many host genes with
420 small effects; see for example diseases listed in Table 2), genetic improvement
421 generally happens at a slower rate, with less obvious effects on disease prevalence
422 (and thus on herd resilience) in subsequent generations. The long-term effects of
423 breeding for increased resistance (and for any other trait) are cumulative and
424 permanent. But because the benefits only occur in subsequent generations, breeding
425 is mostly considered as a complementary control strategy to vaccination or other short-
426 term control measures (Bishop and Woolliams 2014).

427

428 ***Impact of selective breeding for disease resistance on herd resilience***

429 In contrast to the vaccine literature, there are very few published studies that have
430 quantified the effects of selective breeding on pathogen transmission from real data.
431 Hence, the exact realized impact of selective breeding for disease resistance on herd
432 resilience is currently not known (Fig. 2, left hand panel).

433 Uncertainty in these effects is exacerbated by the fact that in the animal breeding
434 literature, the term "disease resistance" is not always consistently defined (often also
435 lacking equivalence to epidemiological concepts) and can refer to different
436 components of herd resilience (see Table 1). Given the large data volumes required
437 to estimate genetic parameters with sufficient accuracy for breeding purposes, the
438 specific breeding goal trait representing disease resistance is often determined by the
439 resistance phenotype, i.e. the trait that can be measured. The diversity of resistance
440 phenotypes used may lead to different outcomes for herd resilience. Table 2 shows
441 some examples of resistance phenotypes considered in current breeding programmes
442 and anticipated effects on pathogen transmission and herd resilience. These illustrate
443 that the success of breeding programmes in reducing the transmission of infectious

444 pathogens depends strongly on the resistance phenotype used, and is to a large extent
445 unknown. Consequently, without explicit consideration of all herd resilience
446 components, in particular those relating to pathogen transmission, selective breeding
447 for individual disease resistance as currently practiced, is likely sub-optimal for
448 improving herd resilience.

449
450 INSERT TABLE 2 HERE

451
452
453 ***New approaches enabling selective breeding for improved herd resilience***
454

455 Fig. 2 illustrates the changes to a breeding programme required to shift its breeding
456 objective from improvement of individuals' (often poorly defined) disease resistance
457 towards improvement of herd resilience. This shift entails two fundamental
458 methodological changes to current approaches: (i) the integration of epidemiological
459 models into the quantitative genetics machinery, and (ii) replacement in the selection
460 criterion of current individual disease resistance traits with an index of the herd
461 resilience traits introduced above. The key benefit arising from these changes is that
462 such a breeding programme improves herd resilience based on predictions of selection
463 response in the individual animal traits contributing to herd resilience as well as in
464 disease prevalence at the herd level, that can be validated with real data.

465 The proposed changes in breeding programmes will involve new demands for data
466 recording and computational methods for estimating genetic and epidemiological
467 effects, as outlined below. Recent advances in estimating (and genetically improving)
468 individuals' disease resilience through their resistance or tolerance have been
469 described elsewhere (e.g. Knap and Doeschl-Wilson 2020); hence we focus here on
470 the components of herd disease resilience relating to pathogen transmission.

471

472 INSERT FIG. 2 HERE

473 *Integrating epidemiological models into quantitative genetics models*

474 Breeding programmes are underpinned by a strong body of quantitative genetics
475 theory to estimate genetic and economic effects associated with including specific
476 traits in the selection criterion (Fig. 2). For example, once genetic parameters (e.g.
477 heritability, prediction accuracy) for a particular proxy trait for disease resistance or
478 resilience (denoted 'R-trait' in Fig. 2) have been estimated, the well-known 'breeder's
479 equation' can be used to obtain an estimate for the expected change in the average
480 R-trait value over successive generations of selective breeding (Lush 1937).
481 Quantitative genetics theory alone can however not predict how genetic selection for
482 the R-trait affects pathogen transmission. This is because the relationship between the
483 R-trait and pathogen transmission is non-linear and depends on the animals'
484 susceptibility and the infectivity and duration of infectious period, when infected.
485 Consequently, the impact on pathogen transmission and therefore herd resilience of
486 breeding programmes that build on quantitative genetics theory alone is difficult to
487 predict (as denoted by the large question-mark in the left-hand panel of Fig. 2).

488 Bishop and Stear (1999) were the first to integrate epidemiological theory into
489 quantitative genetics models. Using gastro-intestinal parasitism in sheep, they
490 demonstrated that the breeder's equation vastly underpredicts the response to
491 selection for disease resistance in terms of the population's parasite load when
492 epidemiological effects are ignored. Various genetic-epidemiological models have
493 been developed since to predict how selective breeding reduces the infectious disease
494 incidence or prevalence over successive generations in various animal species,
495 including fish (e.g. MacKenzie and Bishop 2001; Nieuwhoff et al. 2009; Gharbi et al.
496 2015; Raphaka et al. 2018). However, whilst these models have proven extremely

497 useful for demonstrating and quantifying the potential epidemiological effects of
498 selective breeding, they have not been incorporated into current breeding
499 programmes. This is because these models require as input genetic parameter
500 estimates for the underlying animal traits affecting pathogen transmission (e.g.
501 susceptibility to infection, infectivity, duration of infectious period), which until recently
502 have been difficult to estimate from existing data.

503

504 *Estimating genetic effects for the epidemiological animal traits*

505 Some of the disease resistance phenotypes used to date (see e.g. Table 2) may be
506 considered as proxies for susceptibility to infection. However, genetic parameter
507 estimates for infectivity or the duration of the infectious period, or for recovery rate as
508 a proxy of the latter, are extremely scarce. In particular, despite substantial evidence
509 that individuals vary in infectivity (e.g. Velthuis et al. 2002), and that highly infectious
510 super-spreaders are a common phenomenon (Lloyd-Smith et al., 2015), empirical
511 evidence that infectivity is partly under genetic control emerged only very recently
512 (Anacleto et al. 2019). A main reason for this paucity of estimates is that the herd
513 resilience traits relating to pathogen transmission cannot be measured directly. Hence
514 genetic parameter estimates for these traits need to be inferred from data that *can* be
515 measured, such as the resistance phenotypes used in current studies (see e.g. those
516 listed in Table 2). Bishop and Woolliams (2014) outline how the genetic signal can be
517 masked by various sources of noise inherent in these data. Theoretical studies indicate
518 that disentangling genetic effects for susceptibility to infection from those relating to
519 infectivity or recovery either requires additional data or theoretical expansions of the
520 classical linear mixed model machinery. For example, recent studies have expanded
521 conventional quantitative genetics threshold models to enable joint genetic parameter

522 estimation for susceptibility to, and recovery from, mastitis in cattle from routinely
523 collected repeated measures of somatic cell counts (Franzen et al. 2012; Welderufael
524 et al. 2017). These studies indicate that susceptibility and recovery are genetically
525 different traits; it follows that disease data may comprise considerably more genetic
526 variation that can be exploited for -selective breeding, than previously anticipated.

527 **Estimating** genetic effects for infectivity without direct individual measurements of
528 pathogen shedding proves more difficult, because an individual's infectivity affects the
529 infection status of other individuals, and it is usually not known who infects who
530 (Lipschutz-Powell et al. 2012). Several alternative approaches have been proposed to
531 estimate genetic susceptibility and infectivity effects (e.g. Anacleto et al. 2015;
532 Biemans et al. 2017 and 2019a), and more recently to estimate genetic effects for
533 susceptibility, infectivity and recovery rate simultaneously (Pooley et al. 2020). All of
534 these incorporate quantitative genetics methodologies into epidemiological models or
535 vice versa. Although further developments and validation of these methods is ongoing,
536 results from both simulated and real data analyses suggest that it is possible to obtain
537 reasonably accurate and unbiased estimates of genetic effects for these traits from
538 repeated records of individuals' infection and/or survival status given appropriate data
539 structures (e.g. observations from multiple herds or groups of individuals, in the case
540 of infectivity) (Anacleto et al. 2015; Biemans et al. 2017; Pooley et al. 2020). This paves
541 the way for including epidemiological traits and prediction models into a data-driven
542 breeding programme with improved herd disease resilience as its breeding objective,
543 as shown in Fig. 2.

544

545 INSERT FIG. 2 HERE

546

Commented [WA1]: Start from here

547 ***Emerging empirical insights of the epidemiological effects of selective breeding***

548 Although still in their infancy, interesting new empirical insights for herd resilience have
549 already started to emerge from combining genetic and epidemiological methods. For
550 example, analysing endemic claw disease digital dermatitis (DD) data in dairy cattle,
551 Biemans et al. (2019b) demonstrated that it is possible to obtain genomic breeding
552 values for the basic reproduction ratio (R_0) for this complex disease with reasonable
553 accuracy from a limited amount of field data, by accounting for genetic variation in
554 susceptibility and infectivity. IPN virus transmission experiments in Atlantic salmon
555 revealed that individuals carrying the beneficial allele for IPN resistance (i.e. conferring
556 lower mortality following exposure) had both lower susceptibility to IPN virus infection
557 and lower infectivity, but also tended to die sooner when infected (i.e. had shorter
558 infectious periods) (Doeschl-Wilson et al. 2018). This extremely fortunate combination
559 of allelic effects may explain the observed success of existing breeding programmes
560 to drastically reduce IPN outbreaks within a few years of selection, exceeding
561 expectations based on quantitative genetics theory (Hjeltnes et al. 2018). However,
562 this fortunate combination does not always apply. In a similar transmission experiment
563 for Infectious Salmon Anaemia virus (ISAV) in Atlantic salmon, animals that differed in
564 their estimated genomic breeding value for ISA resistance (GEBV, based on mortality
565 records from previous ISAV challenge tests) did not differ significantly in their
566 susceptibility to ISAV infection (Chase-Topping-et al. 2021). However, individuals with
567 high resistance GEBVs tended to have lower infectivity and a higher chance to recover
568 or survive the infection, indicating that selection for ISA resistance improves survival
569 and reduces transmission of ISAV infected fish. Interestingly, in this study the
570 estimated genetic effects on virus transmission were stronger than the vaccine effects,

571 indicating that vaccination alone may not always be the most efficient method to
572 improve herd resilience.

573
574

575 **5. Conclusions**

576 Disease control efforts should focus on herd resilience rather than on individual
577 resilience. The importance of improved evaluations of vaccination and breeding
578 programmes with respect to their influence on pathogen transmission cannot be
579 emphasized enough. Evidence presented above shows that to date we have limited
580 understanding of the impact of either vaccination or selective breeding on herd
581 resilience, as the effects on pathogen transmission are not fully understood. In
582 particular, the results from empirical and simulation studies suggest that the potential
583 contribution of selective breeding to reducing the transmission of infectious pathogens
584 and thus on herd resilience is not yet realized. Also, very few studies to date have
585 assessed the combined effects of vaccination and selective breeding on infectious
586 disease prevalence and impact, although both methods are frequently applied jointly.
587 To remedy these short-comings and design more effective vaccines or breeding goals
588 for herd disease resilience, a paradigm shift of our current approaches to control
589 infectious disease in livestock may be required. This shift would include routinely
590 carried out transmission experiments or field studies coupled with (genetic-)
591 epidemiological models to not only capture the direct effects of selective breeding or
592 vaccination on individual resilience to infectious diseases, but also on the indirect
593 effects on herd resilience mediated through pathogen transmission. In addition,
594 assessment of vaccination or selective breeding for herd resilience traits on pathogen
595 evolution is paramount for long-term success of these strategies. Progress in these
596 areas requires closer collaboration between the disciplines of infection and immunity,

597 animal breeding and epidemiology, including greater harmonisation in terminologies,

598 as exemplified in this article.

599

600

601

602 **Ethics approval**

603 Not applicable; this article only presents previously published experimental and field
604 data

605 **Data and model availability statement [Arial 12 bold, style 'ANM heading 1']**

606 Not applicable; this article only presents previously published experimental and field
607 data

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613 **Author contributions**

614 ADW: Conceived the study and composed the first draft. PK, TO and SM contributed
615 to all sections of the paper and read and approved the final version

616 **Declaration of interest**

617 The authors declare no conflict of interest

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Commented [WA2]: Simon, please insert your grant references.

628 **References [Arial 12 bold, style 'ANM heading 1']**

629 Adams, A., 2019. Progress, challenges and opportunities in fish vaccine
630 development. *Fish & shellfish immunology* 90, pp.210-214.

631 Albers, G.A.A., Gray, G.D., Piper, L.R., Barker, J.S.F., Le Jambre, L.F., Barger, I.A.,
632 1987. The genetics of resistance and resilience to *Haemonchus contortus*
633 infection in young Merino sheep. *International journal for parasitology* 17(7),
634 pp.1355-1363.

635 Allen, A.R., Skuce, R.A., Byrne, A.W., 2018. Bovine tuberculosis in Britain and
636 Ireland—A perfect storm? the confluence of potential ecological and
637 epidemiological impediments to controlling a chronic infectious disease.
638 *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 5, p.109.

639 Anacleto, O., Garcia-Cortés, L.A., Lipschutz-Powell, D., Woolliams, J.A., Doeschl-
640 Wilson, A.B., 2015. A novel statistical model to estimate host genetic effects
641 affecting disease transmission. *Genetics* 201(3), pp.871-884.

642 Anacleto, O., Cabaleiro, S., Villanueva, B., Saura, M., Houston, R.D., Woolliams,
643 J.A., Doeschl-Wilson, A.B., 2019. Genetic differences in host infectivity affect
644 disease spread and survival in epidemics. *Scientific reports*, 9(1), pp.1-12.

645 Anderson, R. M., R. M. May, 1991. *Infectious Diseases of Humans:*

646 Dynamics and Control. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.

647 Anche, M.T., De Jong, M.C.M., Bijma, P., 2014. On the definition and utilization of
648 heritable variation among hosts in reproduction ratio R_0 for infectious diseases.
649 Heredity 113(4), pp.364-374.

650 Aznar, I., McGrath, G., Murphy, D., Corner, L.A., Gormley, E., Frankena, K., More,
651 S.J., Martin, W., O'Keeffe, J., De Jong, M.C., 2011. Trial design to estimate the
652 effect of vaccination on tuberculosis incidence in badgers. Veterinary
653 microbiology 151(1-2), pp.104-111.

654 Aznar, I., Frankena, K., More, S.J., O'Keeffe, J., McGrath, G., Jong, M.C.M.D., 2018.
655 Quantification of Mycobacterium bovis transmission in a badger vaccine field
656 trial. Preventive Veterinary Medicine 149, pp. 29–37.

657 Bacon, L.D., Hunt, H.D., Cheng, H.H., 2001. Genetic resistance to Marek's disease.
658 In Marek's Disease (ed. K. Hirai). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany. pp.
659 121-141

660 Banos, G., Winters, M., Mrode, R., Mitchell, A.P., Bishop, S.C., Woolliams, J.A.,
661 Coffey, M.P., 2017. Genetic evaluation for bovine tuberculosis resistance in
662 dairy cattle. Journal of dairy science 100(2), pp.1272-1281.

663 Bailey, R.I., Cheng, H.H., Chase-Topping, M., Mays, J.K., Anacleto, O., Dunn, J.R.,
664 Doeschl-Wilson, A., 2020. Pathogen transmission from vaccinated hosts can
665 cause dose-dependent reduction in virulence. PLoS biology 18(3), p.e3000619.

666 Beldomenico, P.M., 2020. Do superspreaders generate new superspreaders? a
667 hypothesis to explain the propagation pattern of COVID-19. International
668 Journal of Infectious Diseases 96, pp.461-463.

669 Biemans, F., de Jong, M.C., Bijma, P., 2017. A model to estimate effects of SNPs on
670 host susceptibility and infectivity for an endemic infectious disease. *Genetics*
671 *Selection Evolution* 49(1), p.53.

672 Biemans, F., de Jong, M.C.M., Bijma, P., 2019a. A genome-wide association study
673 for susceptibility and infectivity of Holstein Friesian dairy cattle to digital
674 dermatitis. *Journal of dairy science* 102(7), pp.6248-6262.

675 Biemans, F., de Jong, M.C.M., Bijma, P., 2019b. A genome-wide association study
676 for susceptibility and infectivity of Holstein Friesian dairy cattle to digital
677 dermatitis. *Journal of dairy science*, 102(7), pp.6248-6262.

678 Bishop, S.C., Stear, M.J., 1999. Genetic and epidemiological relationships between
679 productivity and disease resistance: gastro-intestinal parasite infection in
680 growing lambs. *Animal Science* 69(3), pp.515-524.

681 Bishop, S.C., 2010. Disease resistance: genetics. In *Encyclopedia of Animal Science*
682 (eds. W.G. Pond, A.W. Bell). Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York (2010), pp. 288-
683 290

684 Bishop, S.C., 2012. A consideration of resistance and tolerance for ruminant
685 nematode infections. *Frontiers in Genetics* 3, p.168.

686 Bishop, S.C., Woolliams, J.A., 2014. Genomics and disease resistance studies in
687 livestock. *Livestock science* 166, pp.190-198.

688 Bisset, S.A., Morris, C.A., 1996. Feasibility and implications of breeding sheep for
689 resilience to nematode challenge. *International journal for parasitology* 26(8-9),
690 pp.857-868.

691 Bitsouni, V., Lycett, S., Opriessnig, T., Doeschl-Wilson, A., 2019. Predicting vaccine
692 effectiveness in livestock populations: A theoretical framework applied to PRRS
693 virus infections in pigs. *PLoS one* 14(8), p.e0220738.

694 Blanc, F., Ollion, E., Puillet, L., Delaby, L., Ingrand, S., Tichit, M., Friggens, N.C.,
695 2013. Evaluation quantitative de la robustesse des animaux et du troupeau:
696 quels principes retenir. Rencontres Autour des Recherches sur les Ruminants
697 20, pp.265-272.

698 Boddicker, N.J., Garrick, D.J., Rowland, R.R.R., Lunney, J.K., Reecy, J.M., Dekkers,
699 J.C.M., 2014. Validation and further characterization of a major quantitative trait
700 locus associated with host response to experimental infection with porcine
701 reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus. *Animal Genetics* 45(1), pp.48-58.

702 Børgwald, J., Dalmo, R.A., 2019. Review on Immersion Vaccines for Fish: An Update
703 2019. *Microorganisms*, 7(12), p.627.

704 Chase-Topping, M., Xie, J., Pooley, C., Trus, I., Bonckaert, C., Rediger, K., Bailey,
705 R.I., Brown, H., Bitsouni, V., Barrio, M.B., Gueguen, S., Doeschl-Wilson, A.
706 2020. New insights about vaccine effectiveness: Impact of attenuated PRRS-
707 strain vaccination on heterologous strain transmission. *Vaccine*.

708 Chase-Topping M., Pooley C., Moghadam H., Hillestad B., Lillehammer M., Sveen L.,
709 Doeschl-Wilson A., 2021. Impact of vaccination and selective breeding on the
710 transmission of Infectious Salmon Anemia Virus. *Aquaculture*. Accepted

711 Chong, Y.L., Padhi, A., Hudson, P.J., Poss, M., 2010. The effect of vaccination on
712 the evolution and population dynamics of avian paramyxovirus-1. *PLoS*
713 *Pathogens* 6(4), p.e1000872.

714 Craft, M. E., 2015. Infectious disease transmission and contact networks in wildlife
715 and livestock. *Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series*
716 *B, Biological sciences* 370(1669), 20140107.

717 Colditz, I.G., Hine, B.C., 2016. Resilience in farm animals: biology, management,
718 breeding and implications for animal welfare. *Animal Production Science*
719 56(12), pp.1961-1983.

720 Dadar, M., Dhama, K., Vakharia, V.N., Hoseinifar, S.H., Karthik, K., Tiwari, R.,
721 Khandia, R., Munjal, A., Salgado-Miranda, C., Joshi, S.K., 2017. Advances in
722 aquaculture vaccines against fish pathogens: global status and current trends.
723 *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture* 25(3), pp.184-217

724 Dean, N.E., Gsell, P.S., Brookmeyer, R., De Gruttola, V., Donnelly, C.A., Halloran,
725 M.E., Jasseh, M., Nason, M., Riveros, X., Watson, C.H., Henao-Restrepo, A.M.,
726 2019. Design of vaccine efficacy trials during public health emergencies.
727 *Science translational medicine* 11(499), p.eaat0360.

728 Diekmann, O., Heesterbeek, J.A.P., Metz, J.A., 1990. On the definition and the
729 computation of the basic reproduction ratio R_0 in models for infectious
730 diseases in heterogeneous populations. *Journal of mathematical biology* 28(4),
731 pp.365-382.

732 Doeschl-Wilson, A., Anacleto, O., Nielsen, H.M., Karlsson-Drangsholt, T.,
733 Lillehammer, M., Gjerde, B., 2018. New opportunities for genetic disease
734 control: beyond disease resistance. *Proceedings of the World Congress on*
735 *Genetics Applied to Livestock Production*, January 2018, Auckland, 3.462

736 Eblé, P.L., De Koeijer, A.A., De Jong, M.C.M., Engel, B., Dekker, A., 2008. A meta-
737 analysis quantifying transmission parameters of FMDV strain O Taiwan among
738 non-vaccinated and vaccinated pigs. *Preventive veterinary medicine* 83(1),
739 pp.98-106.

740 Boelaert, F., Hugas, M., Ortiz Pelaez, A., Rizzi, V., Stella, P. and Van Der Stede, Y.,
741 2016. The European Union summary report on data of the surveillance of

742 ruminants for the presence of transmissible spongiform encephalopathies
743 (TSEs) in 2015. European Food Safety Authority EFSA Journal 14(12),
744 p.e04643.

745 Franzén, J., Thorburn, D., Urioste, J.I., Strandberg, E., 2012. Genetic evaluation of
746 mastitis liability and recovery through longitudinal analysis of transition
747 probabilities. *Genetics Selection Evolution* 44(1), p.10.

748 Gandon, S., Mackinnon, M.J., Nee, S., Read, A.F., 2001. Imperfect vaccines and the
749 evolution of pathogen virulence. *Nature* 414, 751–756.

750 Gharbi, K., Matthews, L., Bron, J., Roberts, R., Tinch, A., Stear, M., 2015. The
751 control of sea lice in Atlantic salmon by selective breeding. *Journal of the Royal*
752 *Society Interface* 12(110), p.20150574.

753 Gopinath, S., Lichtman, J.S., Bouley, D.M., Elias, J.E., Monack, D.M., 2014. Role of
754 disease-associated tolerance in infectious superspreaders. *Proceedings of the*
755 *National Academy of Sciences* 111(44), pp.15780-15785

756 Hadfield, J., Megill, C., Bell, S.M., Huddleston, J., Potter, B., Callender, C.,
757 Sagulenko, P., Bedford, T., Neher, R.A., 2018. Nextstrain: real-time tracking of
758 pathogen evolution. *Bioinformatics* 34(23), pp.4121-4123.

759 Halloran, M.E., Longini, I.M., Struchiner, C.J., 2010. *Design and Analysis of Vaccine*
760 *Studies*, Springer New York.

761 Hjeltnes, B., Walde, C., Bang Jensen, B. and Haukaas, A., 2019.
762 *Fiskehelse rapporten 2018, Veterinærinstituttets rapportserie 3-2018.*

763 Hope, J.C., Villarreal-Ramos, B., 2008. Bovine TB and the development of new
764 vaccines. *Comparative immunology, microbiology and infectious diseases* 31(2-
765 3), pp.77-100.

766 Horter, D.C., Pogranichniy, R.M., Chang, C.C., Evans, R.B., Yoon, K.J., Zimmerman,
767 J.J., 2002. Characterization of the carrier state in porcine reproductive and
768 respiratory syndrome virus infection. *Veterinary microbiology* 86(3), pp.213-228.

769 Houston, R.D., 2017. Future directions in breeding for disease resistance in
770 aquaculture species. *Revista Brasileira de Zootecnia*, 46(6), pp.545-551.

771 Knap, P.W., Doeschl-Wilson, A., 2020. Why breed disease-resilient livestock, and
772 how?. *Genetics Selection Evolution* 52(1), pp.1-18.

773 Knight-Jones, T.J.D., Rushton, J., 2013. The economic impacts of foot and mouth
774 disease—What are they, how big are they and where do they occur?. *Preventive
775 veterinary medicine* 112(3-4), pp.161-173.

776 Knight-Jones, T. J. D., Edmond, K., Gubbins, S., & Paton, D. J. (2014). Veterinary
777 and human vaccine evaluation methods. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B:
778 Biological Sciences* 281(1784), 20132839.

779 Lindström, T., Lewerin, S. S., Wennergren, U. 2012. Influence on disease spread
780 dynamics of herd characteristics in a structured livestock industry. *Journal of the
781 Royal Society, Interface* 9(71), 1287–1294.

782 Linhares, D.C., Johnson, C. and Morrison, R.B., 2015. Economic analysis of
783 vaccination strategies for PRRS control. *PloS one*, 10(12), p.e0144265.

784 Lipschutz-Powell, D., Woolliams, J.A., Bijma, P., Doeschl-Wilson, A.B., 2012. Indirect
785 genetic effects and the spread of infectious disease: are we capturing the full
786 heritable variation underlying disease prevalence?. *PloS one* 7(6), p.e39551.

787 Lloyd-Smith, J.O., Schreiber, S.J., Kopp, P.E., Getz, W.M., 2005. Superspreading
788 and the effect of individual variation on disease emergence. *Nature* 438(7066),
789 pp.355-359.

790 Longini, I.M., Sagatelian, K., Rida, W.N., Halloran, M.E., 1998. Optimal vaccine trial
791 design when estimating vaccine efficacy for susceptibility and infectiousness
792 from multiple populations. *Statistical Medicine* 17, 1121–1136.

793 Lush, J.L., 1937. *Animal breeding plans*. Animal breeding plans. Iowa State College
794 Press, Ames IA.

795 Luther H. 2018. Pig breeding in Switzerland. European Pig Producers conference, 04
796 June 2018; Sorsee.

797 MacKenzie, K., Bishop, S.C., 2001. Utilizing stochastic genetic epidemiological
798 models to quantify the impact of selection for resistance to infectious diseases
799 in domestic livestock. *Journal of animal science* 79(8), pp.2057-2065.

800 Martin, S.W., O’Keeffe, J., Byrne, A.W., Rosen, L.E., White, P.W. and McGrath, G.,
801 2020. Is moving from targeted culling to BCG-vaccination of badgers (*Meles*
802 *meles*) associated with an unacceptable increased incidence of cattle herd
803 tuberculosis in the Republic of Ireland? A practical non-inferiority wildlife
804 intervention study in the Republic of Ireland (2011-2017). *Preventive Veterinary*
805 *Medicine* 105004.

806 Meeusen, E.N, Walker, J., Peters, A., Pastoret, P.P., Jungersen, G.. 2007. Current
807 status of Vet. vaccines. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews* 20(3), pp. 489–510.

808 Nan, Y., Wu, C., Gu, G., Sun, W., Zhang, Y.J., Zhou, E.M., 2017. Improved vaccine
809 against PRRSV: current progress and future perspective. *Frontiers in*
810 *Microbiology* 8:1635.

811 Nathues, H., Alarcon, P., Rushton, J., Jolie, R., Fiebig, K., Jimenez, M., Geurts, V.,
812 Nathues, C., 2017. Cost of porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus
813 at individual farm level—an economic disease model. *Preventive veterinary*
814 *medicine* 142, pp.16-29.

815 Nikolai, L.A., Meyer, C.G., Kremsner, P.G., Velavan, T.P., 2020. Asymptomatic
816 SARS Coronavirus 2 infection: Invisible yet invincible. *International Journal of*
817 *Infectious Diseases* 100, 112–116.

818 Nieuwhof, G.J., Conington, J., Bishop, S.C., 2009. A genetic epidemiological model
819 to describe resistance to an endemic bacterial disease in livestock: application
820 to footrot in sheep. *Genetics Selection Evolution* 41(1), p.19.

821 Ødegård, J., Baranski, M., Gjerde, B., Gjedrem, T., 2011. Methodology for genetic
822 evaluation of disease resistance in aquaculture species: challenges and future
823 prospects. *Aquaculture research* 42, pp.103-114.

824 Oran, D.P., Topol, E.J., 2020. Prevalence of Asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 Infection: A
825 Narrative Review. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 173(5), pp. 362-367.

826 Orsel, K., Jong, M.C.M. de, Bouma, A., Stegeman, J.A., Dekker, A., 2007. The effect
827 of vaccination on foot and mouth disease virus transmission among dairy cows.
828 *Vaccine* 25, pp.327–335.

829 Parida, S., 2009. Vaccination against foot-and-mouth disease virus: strategies and
830 effectiveness. *Expert review of vaccines* 8(3), pp. 347-365.

831 Pastoret, P.P., 1997. *Veterinary vaccinology*. Elsevier, Amsterdam, The Netherlands.

832 Paton, D. J., Gubbins, S., King, D. P., 2018. Understanding the transmission of foot-
833 and-mouth disease virus at different scales. *Current opinion in virology* 28, pp.
834 85-91.

835 Pileri, E. , Mateu, E., 2016. Review on the transmission porcine reproductive and
836 respiratory syndrome virus between pigs and farms and impact on vaccination.
837 *Veterinary research* 47(1), p.108.

838 Pooley, C.M., Marion, G., Bishop, S.C., Bailey, R.I., Doeschl-Wilson, A.B., 2020.
839 Estimating individuals' genetic and non-genetic effects underlying infectious

840 disease transmission from temporal epidemic data. PLOS Computational
841 Biology, 16(12), p.e1008447.

842 Råberg, L., Graham, A.L., Read, A.F., 2009. Decomposing health: tolerance and
843 resistance to parasites in animals. Philosophical Transactions of the Royal
844 Society B: Biological Sciences 364(1513), pp.37-49.

845 Rahimi, F., Abadi, A.T.B., 2020. Challenges of managing the asymptomatic carriers
846 of SARS-CoV-2. Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease, p.101677.

847 Raphaka, K., Sánchez-Molano, E., Tsairidou, S., Anacleto, O., Glass, E.J.,
848 Woolliams, J.A., Doeschl-Wilson, A., Banos, G., 2018. Impact of genetic
849 selection for increased cattle resistance to bovine tuberculosis on disease
850 transmission dynamics. Frontiers in veterinary science 5, p.237.

851 Read, A.F., Baigent, S.J., Powers, C., Kgosana, L.B., Blackwell, L., Smith, L.P.,
852 Kennedy, D.A., Walkden-Brown, S.W., Nair, V.K., 2015. Imperfect vaccination
853 can enhance the transmission of highly virulent pathogens. PLoS Biology,
854 13(7), p.e1002198.

855 Rose, N., Renson, P., Andraud, M., Paboeuf, F., Le Potier, M.F., Bourry, O., 2015.
856 Porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus (PRRSv) modified-live
857 vaccine reduces virus transmission in experimental conditions. Vaccine 33(21),
858 pp.2493-2499.

859 Shim, E., Galvani, A.P., 2012. Distinguishing vaccine efficacy and effectiveness.
860 Vaccine 30(47), pp.6700-6705.

861 Sommerset, I., Krossøy, B., Biering, E., Frost, P., 2005. Vaccines for fish in
862 aquaculture. Expert review of vaccines 4(1), pp.89-101.

863 Stear, M.J., Bishop, S.C., Mallard, B.A., Raadsma, H., 2001. The sustainability,
864 feasibility and desirability of breeding livestock for disease resistance. *Research*
865 *in veterinary science* 71(1), pp.1-7.

866 Tizard, I. R., 2021. Porcine vaccines. *Vaccines for Veterinarians*, 225–242.e1.

867 Tomley, F.M., Shirley, M.W., 2009. Livestock infectious diseases and zoonoses.
868 *Philosophical Transaction of the Royal Society B*. 364, 1530.

869 Tsairidou, S., Allen, A., Banos, G., Coffey, M., Anacleto, O., Byrne, A.W., Skuce,
870 R.A., Glass, E.J., Woolliams, J.A., Doeschl-Wilson, A.B., 2018. Can we breed
871 cattle for lower bovine TB infectivity?. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 5, p.310.

872 Vale, P.F., McNally, L., Doeschl-Wilson, A., King, K.C., Papat, R., Domingo-
873 Sananes, M.R., Allen, J.E., Soares, M.P., Kümmerli, R., 2016. Beyond
874 killingCan we find new ways to manage infection?. *Evolution, medicine, and*
875 *public health* 2016(1), pp.148-157.

876 VanDerWaal, K.L. & Ezwnea, V.O., 2016. Heterogeneity in pathogen transmission:
877 mechanics and methodology. *Functional Ecology* 30(10), 1606-1622.

878 Velthuis, A.G.J., De Jong, M.C.M., Stockhofe, N., Vermeulen, T.M.M., Kamp, E.M.,
879 2002. Transmission of *Actinobacillus pleuropneumoniae* in pigs is characterized
880 by variation in infectivity. *Epidemiology & Infection* 129(1), pp.203-214.

881 Velthuis, A.G.J., De Jong, M.C.M., Kamp, E.M., Stockhofe, N., Verheijden, J.H.M.,
882 2003. Design and analysis of an *Actinobacillus pleuropneumoniae* transmission
883 experiment. *Preventive veterinary medicine* 60(1), pp.53-68.

884 Van Roermund, H.J.W., Eble, P.L., de Jong, M.C.M., Dekker, A., 2010. No between-
885 open transmission of foot-and-mouth disease virus in vaccinated pigs. *Vaccine*
886 28(28), pp.4452-4461.

887 Welderufael, B.G., de Koning, D.J., Janss, L.L.G., Franzén, J., Fikse, W.F., 2016.
888 Simultaneous genetic evaluation of simulated mastitis susceptibility and
889 recovery ability using a bivariate threshold sire model. *Acta Agriculturae*
890 *Scandinavica*, Section A—Animal Science 66(3), pp.125-134.

891 Witter, R.L., 1997. Increased virulence of Marek's disease virus field isolates. *Avian*
892 *diseases*, pp.149-163.

893 Witter, R.L., 2001. Protective efficacy of Marek's disease vaccines. In *Marek's*
894 *Disease* (ed. K. Hirai). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany, pp. 57-90).

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897 **Table 1 Glossary of terminology**

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Term	Definition	Comments
Epidemiological concepts		
Infection	An invasion of an animal by an infectious pathogen	
Disease	A disorder of structure or function of an infected animal	
Susceptible animal	An animal that is at risk of becoming infected by an infectious pathogen	
Resistance to infection	Propensity to not become infected when exposed to infectious pathogens	In contrast, susceptibility to infection is the propensity to become infected when exposed to infectious pathogens
Resistance to disease	Propensity to not develop disease when infected	In contrast, susceptibility to disease is the propensity to not develop disease when infected
Vaccine efficacy	The ability of a vaccine to provide protection against disease under ideal conditions (e.g. during a clinical trial).	An individual-level measure of vaccine effect, defined as the reduction in incidence of the target infection/disease in vaccinated participants compared to controls ¹
Vaccination effectiveness	Efficacy of the vaccine under real-world conditions	A population measure of vaccine effect, defined as vaccine efficacy multiplied by vaccine coverage (% of the population vaccinated). Often considered to include indirect vaccine effects on transmission ²
Reproduction number R (R value)	Average number of secondary cases produced by a typical infectious individual during its infectious lifetime	If $R < 1$, the infection will decline and eventually die out.
Animal production and breeding concepts		
Recoverability	The degree and rate of return to the health and	Considers both the duration of disease and the potential

¹ Dean et al. 2019² Shim and Galvani 2001

	performance state prior to exposure	for residual effects on health or production performance following disease recovery
Resilience (generic)	Capacity to be minimally affected by disturbances or to rapidly return to the state pertained before exposure to a disturbance ³	
Disease resilience (individual, herd or system)	(1) capacity to be minimally affected by exposure to infection or to rapidly return to the pre-exposure state (2) ability of animals to maintain high production performance when challenged by infection ⁴	Adapted from the generic definition above
Component traits of <i>individual disease resilience</i>		These are direct effects, acting on the resilience of the individual itself
Disease resistance	Ability of the individual to inhibit or limit within-host pathogen replication ⁵	This definition encompasses the epidemiological concepts of resistance to infection. There is inconsistency in the use of this term in the animal breeding literature, where it has referred to resistance to infection, to resistance to disease, or to mortality following exposure
Disease tolerance	Ability of an infected host to reduce the impact of infection on performance and health, i.e. maintain high health or production performance at a given within-host pathogen load ⁵	Tolerance can only be expressed once an animal has become infected and therefore expression of tolerance is conditional on susceptibility to infection. Tolerance encompasses the epidemiological concept of resistance to disease, as well as recoverability

Component traits of *herd disease resilience*

Direct effects, affecting an individual's own fitness, health and performance

³ Colditz and Hine 2016

⁴ Albers et al 1987

⁵ Raberg et al. 2009; Bishop 2012

Individual disease resilience	As defined above	The component traits include resistance and tolerance (as defined above)
<i>Indirect effects</i> , i.e. additional components relating to environmental pathogen load, with the potential to affect the health and performance of susceptible herd members		
Susceptibility to infection	As defined above, under epidemiological concepts	This is also a direct effect
Magnitude of infectiousness	Propensity of an infected individual to transmit infection to a typical (average) susceptible individual	Also referred to as host 'infectivity' ⁶ ; relates to the nature and amount of pathogen shedding per unit of time
Duration of infectious period		Relates to the duration of pathogen shedding. It is equal to the inverse of the recovery rate if the duration of the infectious period and the duration of disease are equal

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⁶ Velthuis et al. 2002; Lipschutz-Powell et al. 2012

902 **Table 2 Examples for genetic selection for disease resistance considered in**
 903 **current breeding programmes, and their potential effect on pathogen**
 904 **transmission and herd resilience**
 905

Disease & Species	Resistance phenotype	Characteristics of a resistant animal	Effects on pathogen transmission and herd resilience
Bovine Tuberculosis (bTB) in cattle	Binary infection status from in-vivo diagnostic skin test applied in herds exposed to bTB	Less likely to have a positive test result when exposed to bTB ⁷	Some uncertainty in whether genetically more resistant cows are less likely to become infected and to transmit bTB ⁸
Mareks disease (MD) in poultry	Clinical signs (e.g. lameness, lesions) and mortality after exposure to MD virus in challenge trials	Less likely to develop clinical MD and subsequently die ⁹	Chicken with high genetic resistance can still become infected and transmit the MD virus ⁹ . Unknown if breeding for MD resistance reduces MDV transmission
Viral and bacterial infections in Atlantic salmon	Binary survival or time of death after pathogen exposure in challenge trials	Less likely to die when exposed to the pathogen in consideration ¹⁰	Unknown whether fish considered genetically more resistant have greater disease resistance or tolerance, or both. Unknown if breeding for disease resistance reduces pathogen transmission.
Gastro-intestinal parasite resistance in ruminants	Parasite egg count in feces (Fecal egg counts, FEC)	Lower FEC may reflect the ability of an animal to limit parasite establishment, growth, fecundity and / or shedding ¹¹	Breeding for disease resistance reduces parasite shedding and thus the environmental parasite load, with beneficial effects on herd resilience ¹²
Porcine Reproductive & Respiratory Syndrome (PPRS) in pigs ¹³	Blood viral load of pigs over 21 day infection period after inoculation with the PRRS virus	Pigs that carry the beneficial (GBP5) allele associated with greater natural ¹⁴ PRRS resistance are still susceptible to PRRSV infection by inoculation, but tend	Unknown if pigs that carry the GBP5 resistance allele are more resistant to infection and less infectious when infected in natural challenge conditions. Hence the effect of genetic selection on PRRS virus transmission is unknown.

⁷ Banos et al. 2017

⁸ Bishop and Woolliams, 2014

⁹ Bacon et al. 2001

¹⁰ Ødegård et al. 2011

¹¹ Bisset and Morris 1996

¹² Stear et al. 2001

¹³ Currently included in genetic evaluations, but not explicitly included in the formal selection criteria

¹⁴ As opposed to resistance through gene editing, which confers full resistance to PRRSV infection.

to have lower virus
replication¹⁵

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¹⁵ Boddicker et al. 2014

908 **Figure captions**

909 **Fig. 1. A conceptual model of herd disease resilience.** Herd disease resilience
910 depends on (i) each animal's individual disease resilience (represented here by size:
911 larger animals are more resilient, with the contributing mechanism outlined for each
912 individual below) and on (ii) its contribution to the environmental pathogen load that
913 susceptible animals in the herd are exposed to (represented here by the number of
914 pathogen particles). Item (ii) is influenced by factors relating to the pathogen (innate
915 characteristics including transmission potential) and by the host (susceptibility to
916 infection, magnitude of infectiousness, duration of infectious period). In the context of
917 the epidemiological SIR (Susceptible-Infectious-Recovered) model, where infected
918 animals are assumed infectious until they reach the recovered state and have long-
919 lasting immunity, these give rise to three epidemiological animal traits relating to
920 pathogen transmission that influence herd resilience: *susceptibility* (among susceptible
921 individuals: the probability of infection given exposure), *infectivity* (or magnitude of
922 infectiousness) (among infected individuals: the nature and amount of pathogen
923 shedding per unit time) and the duration of the *infectious period*, with levels indicated
924 in the figure by the animal's position relative to the corresponding wedges

- 925 • Susceptible animal A has higher individual resilience than animal B because it
926 is less susceptible to infection than animal B. As animal A is less likely to
927 become infected given exposure, it is also less likely to contribute to the
928 environmental pathogen load: its expected positive impact on herd resilience is
929 greater than that of individual B.
- 930 • Infected animal D has a higher individual resilience than infected animal C as it
931 is able to maintain high production performance (i.e. high tolerance) despite of
932 a long infected/infectious period. But animal D contributes more strongly to the

933 environmental pathogen load due to both a longer infectious period and higher
934 infectivity, therefore, it has a greater negative impact on herd resilience than
935 animal C.

936 • Recovered animal E has lower individual resilience than animal F as it does not
937 fully return to its pre-exposure state. Recovered animals no longer contribute to
938 the environmental pathogen load, hence have no epidemiological impact on
939 herd resilience.

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943 **Fig. 2. Scheme of a potential future breeding programme with improved herd**
944 **disease resilience as its breeding objective, contrasted to current approaches**
945 **focusing on improved (individual) disease resistance or resilience.**

946 Current approaches are in grey (left), proposed future approach is in yellow (right).

947 Innovative components are highlighted in bold.

948 ¹ These herd resilience traits may include individual resilience as well as host traits
949 controlling pathogen transmission, such as susceptibility to infection, infectivity and
950 duration of the infectious period (see Table 1 and Fig. 1).

951 ² The disease phenotypes collected may be the same as in the current breeding
952 programmes, or new measures as new diagnostics become available.

953 ³ Improved statistical models that incorporate genetic and epidemiological theory will
954 be used to estimate genetic effects for the diverse herd resilience traits, and their
955 genetic relationship, from observable disease phenotypes (see section 'Estimating
956 genetic effects for the epidemiological animal traits' for further information).

957 ⁴ This can be assessed using genetic-epidemiological simulation models (see section
958 'Integrating epidemiological models into quantitative genetics models' for further
959 information).

960 ⁵ It may not be necessary to explicitly include all herd resilience traits into the selection
961 index depending on their heritabilities, genetic correlations and prediction accuracies.

962 ⁶ The size of the question mark symbolises the degree of uncertainty in the outcome
963 of the decision with respect to whether the breeding objective is achieved. We expect
964 this uncertainty to reduce drastically for breeding programmes that include
965 epidemiological components.

